

The Study on Investor's Attitude towards Mutual Fund

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ABSTRACT:

A Research Paper on the study of Investor's Attitude towards Mutual Fund on current scenario. Mutual funds is simplify in one word is called as Mediator or Intermediaries. Mutual Fund is saving option for investor. This Research Paper given me great learning experience give various aspects like objectives, research of study, I got brief knowledge from this Research Paper. It helps me to understand different people view about Mutual Fund. It also helps me to understand which time is best for investment and how Mutual Fund is risky but more profitable than other investment.

Keywords: Mutual Fund, Investor, Risk, Performace Evaluation, Attitude

1. INTRODUCTION

Mutual funds are intermediaries to take benefits of share market. Directly investing in the share market is more risky. In this scenario mutual fund help to get low risk and make money from share market.

Growth and Development of Mutual Funds:

The idea of pooling money together for investing purposes started in Europe in the middle of the 19th century. The first pooled fund in the U.S. was created in 1893 for the faculty and staff of Harvard University. The first official mutual fund, Massachusetts Investors Trust was started in March 1924.

The genesis of Mutual Funds in India can be traced to the year when the Indian Parliament enacted the Unit Trust of India (UTI) Act. The significance of the establishment of UTI Act which reads as : An Act to provide for the establishment of a Corporation with a view to encouraging saving and investment and participation in the income, profit and gains accruing to the corporation from the acquisition holding, management, and disposal of Securities”. Thus, with the establishment of UTI, the seeds were sown for the emergence of a vibrant Mutual Funds Industry in India.

Benefit of Study:

It Help to understand the behaviors of investor
Its provide a view of investor towards mutual fund

2. OBJECTIVE OF STUDY:

1. To identify investors view about mutual Fund.
2. To understand behavior of investor while selection of investment plan.
3. To understand different types of investment plan.
4. To understand why mutual fund is best for long term investment.
5. To understand Investors view on different types of investment

3. RESEARCHMETHODOLOGY:

The study is based on descriptive research design. Research is based on primary and secondary.

1. **Primary Data:** The survey has been done on selected people.
2. **Secondary Data:** The Research Paper is based on the secondary data has been collected from various journals and websites.

Sample Size: 50

4. DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

Data Analysis is done on the basis of the information collected from the Respondents and following Parameters are selected for the Data Analysis.

1. AGE GROUP

Interpretation:

Out of 50 Investors

22 % are in the Age Group of 18 – 30

45% are in the Age Group of 30 – 40

33% are in the Age Group of 40 & Above

2. ANNUAL INCOME

Interpretation:

8 % - Annual Income is between 1 Lac. To 2 Lac.

62% - Annual Income is between 2 Lac. To 3 Lac.

15% - Annual Income is between 3 Lac. To 4 Lac.

15% - Annual Income is between Above 4 Lac.

3. SAFEST OPTION FOR INVESTMENT

Interpretation:

44 % - Bank Deposit

25% - Mutual Fund

12% - Share Market

19% - Gold

4. INVESTMENT IN MUTUAL FUND

Findings

78% - Yes

22% - No

5. WHY NOT INVESTING IN MUTUAL FUND

Findings

8 % - Not Easy to Understand

50% - Don't have knowledge

17% - No Interest

25% - Other

6. PREFERRED ASSET MANAGEMENT COMPANY

Findings

16% - SBI Mutual Fund

25 % - Axis Mutual Fund

17 % - HDFC Mutual Fund

12 % - ICICI Mutual Fund

30% - Other

7. INVEST FOR SHORT TERM OR LONG TERM

Findings

32 % - Short Term

68 % - Long Term

8. FACTORS EFFECT INVESTMENT DECISION

Findings

46% High Risk

20% Professional Management

13% Liquidity

21% Other

5. FINDINGS

1. Many people have aware about Mutual Fund but don't have proper knowledge.
2. Investors are always having concern about risk factor.
3. Most on the people invest money in mutual fund due to Tax exemption
4. Most of the people like to invest in bank scheme.

6. SUGGESTION:

1. Need to aware about mutual fund different scheme.
2. Government need to promote mutual fund companies.
3. There are some applications which are useful for mutual fund investment.
4. Companies need to make brand building activity.
5. SIP is better option to invest in Mutual Fund.

7. CONCLUSION:

The Research Entitled “A RESEARCH PAPER REPORT ON THE STUDY ON INVESTOR’S ATTITUDE TOWARDS MUTUAL FUND.” Included A Study Of Investor Behavior.

Mutual Fund Is Great Option For Long Term Investment. It Is Risky But It Will More Profitable And Other Investment. SIP Is Also A Better Option For Investment In Mutual Fund.

8. REFERENCES:

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